

A new Decision Support Tool for assessing cities sustainability levels: the IBTool software.

Giuliano Poli^{1,*}, Stefano Cuntò¹, Dario De Vita²

1 Department of Architecture, University of Naples Federico II, Via Toledo 402, 80134 Napoli, Italy; giuliano.poli@unina.it; stefano.cuntò@unina.it

2 IT consultant on the Research Project of National Relevance (PRIN) GLOSSA at Department of Architecture, University of Naples Federico II, Via Toledo 402, 80134 Napoli, Italy; devitadario@gmail.com

* corresponding author

Keywords

*Neighbourhood
Sustainability Assessment
Tools (NSATs), digital tools,
Decision Support Systems
(DSS), SDG 11 Key
Performance Indicators
(KPI), MCDA.*

Abstract

Digital Tools for urban sustainability and Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment Tools (NSATs), designed to certify and promote sustainable development initiatives at both neighbourhood and building scales, are gaining increasing relevance in supporting and facilitating city monitoring and transformation processes. These tools can generate enabling impacts on street-level bureaucracy and enhance the capacity of Public Administrations (PAs) to pursue local sustainability goals aligned with the directives of the 2030 Agenda. However, data fragmentation, limited availability, and difficulties in calculating urban-scale indicators often hinder their definition and monitoring. In such a context, it becomes essential to identify Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are consistent with territorial specificities and effectively measure sustainability performance. In response to this need, the Research Project of National Relevance (PRIN) GLOSSA has developed an open-source software called IBTool, which functions as a Decision Support System (DSS) based on the Goal 11 indicators of the SDGs. IBTool is designed to assist PAs in collaborative processes of KPI validation, selection, and weighting, integrating clustering algorithms and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to evaluate the sustainability performance of neighbourhoods and buildings, as well as the impacts of projects at different scales. The aim of this contribution is to show the architecture and development phases of IBTool, designed to combine scientific robustness, operational flexibility, and multi-level approaches in line with the 2030 Agenda.

1. Introduction

Digital tools designed to assess sustainability performance at the urban scale can have significant impacts on Public Administrations (PAs) in terms of work reorganization, reduction in decision-making discretion at various levels, and support for operational choices aimed at achieving the sustainability targets underpinning urban agendas (Phillis et al., 2017).

The balance of ecological, social, and economic capitals as a paradigm of sustainable cities, within a strong sustainability framework (Victor et al., 1998; Cerreta et al., 2014), is hindered not only by the uneven distribution of economic resources but, more importantly, by management gaps that can generate various types of negative externalities (Camagni et al., 1998). Consequently, it becomes necessary to identify priority

objectives through inclusive and structured processes for validating relevant performance and impact indicators for urban transformations. It requires methodological approaches that ensure active engagement from different stakeholders and the reliability of variables used to assess urban development dynamics (Poveda & Lipsett, 2011). To define priorities effectively, it is essential to analyse the specific context, local needs, and place-based indicators capturing the complexity of urban settings (Fusco Girard et al., 2014). This process relies on empirical data, scenarios planning, and dialogue among public-private actors, local communities, specialists and academic institutions (Mecca et al., 2023). An inclusive approach ensures that decisions reflect a shared vision, incorporating diverse perspectives and addressing a wide range of needs. Furthermore, the validation of performance and impact indicators plays a crucial role in measuring the effectiveness of urban transformations and policy (Dizdaoglu, 2017). This requires a structured process based on indicators selection and empirical data comparisons, ensuring that KPIs are relevant, measurable, and capable of capturing the real effects of urban policies in terms of accessibility, social inclusion and economic efficiency as recommended by SDGs.

The impact of digital innovation on urban transition processes involving PAs has long been the subject of debate in several countries worldwide (Carter et al., 2022). These impacts are conceived as the ways in which technological tools are employed and how work reorganization occurs at both tactical and operational levels (Orlikowski & Iacono, 2001).

Observing a lack of empirical research on the different types of technologies and the ways digital transitions influence the work of PAs, Marienfeldt et al. (2024) highlighted that this field of inquiry requires thorough exploration, particularly concerning the impacts of technological transitions on *street-level bureaucracy*. The three prevailing theses regarding the use of digital tools are, thus, the reductionist (i), enabling (ii), and continuity (iii) theses. The first (i) warns against the risks of technological control that could reduce the prerogatives of *street-level bureaucracy*. The enabling thesis (ii) envisions professional enhancement through broader access to information and relief from redundant and repetitive tasks. The third thesis (iii) emphasizes how *street-level bureaucracy* can resist or circumvent regulations to safeguard its discretion, highlighting the coping strategies adopted in the digital era (Marienfeldt et al., 2024).

In the context of PAs, digital tools can be categorized based on their function in decision-making processes, distinguishing between support, guidance, and decisive tools. Traditional technologies, such as digital archives and databases, play a supportive role (Henriksen, 2017), facilitating rapid documentation and structured access to information. Digital assessment tools, such as Decision Support Systems (DSS) (Simon, 2012; Keenan & Jankowski, 2019), Group Support Systems (GSS) (Ackermann & Eden, 2021), Neighbourhood Sustainability Assessment Tools (NSATs) (Pulgar Rubilar et al., 2023; Dawodu et al., 2022), or Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) (Cinelli et al., 2020), serve a guiding function by providing data and operational procedures useful for making informed and conscious decisions (Busch & Henriksen, 2018). Finally, automation, algorithms, and Artificial Intelligence support the adoption of Intelligent Decision Support Systems (I-DSS) (Greco et al., 2022), assuming a decisive role (Bullock, 2019).

Technological advancements in knowledge-sharing mechanisms and data processing for PAs are particularly evident in GOAL 17 (SDG17), which advocates for more accurate target monitoring to effectively guide sustainable urban transformations within a partnership framework from local to global scales (Bachmann et al., 2022). From this perspective, evaluation and DSS that complement purely economic metrics, built on robust statistical and mathematical foundations, enable the identification of the most urgent intervention areas and the assessment of policy impacts from the regional to the district scale. Integrated into decision-making processes, digital tools also offer the ability to process and visualize real-time data, simulate

alternative scenarios, and promote evidence-based decision-making, positioning cities as protagonists of transformative change (Kitchin et al., 2015).

This contribution is framed within the Research Project of National Relevance (PRIN) GLOSSA – *GLOcal knowledge-System for Sustainability Assessment of urban projects*, funded in 2022 by the Italian Ministry of Public Education and coordinated by the *Politecnico di Torino* (POLITO) in cooperation with the University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) and the University of Cagliari (UNICA). The fundamental objective of GLOSSA is to define a knowledge system that supports PAs in decision-making processes aimed at territorial monitoring and the selection of sustainable urban transformation projects, utilizing established or innovative evaluation methodologies based on the indicators of SDG11.

SDG11 of the 2030 Agenda represents one of the key areas of action to enhance the performance, transparency, and shareability of city planning and management processes through sustainability target monitoring and impact assessment in urban transformation choices (Lami et al., 2024).

Emerging research trends on NSATs, aimed at assessing urban sustainability through SDG11 indicators, reveal significant advancements that emphasize the need to explore sustainability not only at the building level but also through an upscaling approach to better capture the complexities of the urban environment and the relationship between individual buildings and neighbourhoods (Bottero et al., 2019; Abastante, 2023). Specifically, Zamanidou et al. (2024) found that 44% of the sustainability frameworks reviewed consider technological implementation and stakeholder engagement as priorities for substantiating assessments, while 17% focus on the interdependencies of urban infrastructures (Zamanidou et al., 2024). Meanwhile, Mirani (2023) underscores the importance of using context-specific indicators that enhance the relevance and applicability of NSATs in different urban contexts (Mirani, 2023). Finally, the combined adoption of top-down and bottom-up methodological approaches fosters local expertise and PAs involvement in evaluation processes, ensuring the inclusion of community needs and their specific conditions (Panosso et al., 2023).

The tripartition of digital tools proposed by Marienfeldt et al. (2024) has been one of the premises for developing a DSS, conceived as an integrated open-source toolbox intended for PAs to assess sustainability levels based on SDG11 targets and, thus, select preferable transformation alternatives in terms of sustainability performance.

The software, developed by the GLOSSA research team and named the *Indicators-Based Tool* (IBTool), serves as a tool designed to support and guide the various phases characterizing a decision-making process, ensuring structured access to information and promoting the effective use of sustainability indicators. The system is not intended to be a decisive tool, meaning it does not aim to replace the Decision Maker (DM) in choices but rather to foster consensus within a working group and provide guidelines to orient project choices at the urban and building scale within an integrated sustainability perspective.

IBTool not only integrates NSATs functionality but has been also conceived as a Group Support System (GSS) in collaborative settings since the publicly displayed model serves as a "transitional object" (Ackermann & Eden, 2021). This concept is particularly pertinent to the overall software development process which functions as a dynamic intermediary facilitating the fluid transition between individual and collective viewpoints. The continuous evolution of the model mirrors the group's shifting perspectives, fostering a seamless integration of diverse insights without exerting undue pressure on individual participants. Indeed, a typical IBTool-supported session begins with the systematic capture of individual contributions, which are then projected onto a shared display. This process naturally leads to modifications—edits, additions, and deletions—that progressively transform an initial, fragmented set of inputs into a coherent representation of

the group's emerging consensus. Crucially, this iterative refinement process occurs in a way that respects the organic nature of idea development, allowing viewpoints to evolve naturally rather than being forcibly aligned from the outset.

Section 2 highlights two research questions and main objectives of this contribution, which aims to show the GLOSSA knowledge system through the explanation of the fundamental steps at the basis of IBTool software development.

2. Objectives and research questions

Within the above mentioned research framework, a prototype of *decision support tool* has been developed, capable of integrating NSATs at both the neighbourhood and building scales into multi-criteria decision-making processes, supporting PAs in the key phases of project evaluation and territorial monitoring.

The GLOSSA research project includes experimental testing in the three geographical areas corresponding to the research units involved in the project. The first test aims to assess the level of sustainability achieved in three neighbourhoods in the city of Cagliari, selected based on their specific socio-economic and demographic characteristics, through the construction of composite sustainability indices. The second test involves comparing urban transformation projects within the metropolitan city of Turin based on sustainability performance linked to SDG11. Finally, the third test applies IBTool to various urban projects and planning interventions currently shaping the territory of Bacoli, in the province of Naples, to evaluate the effectiveness of the software as a tool for measuring direct impacts in collaboration with local administrations.

Two key research questions have provided the foundation for some of the methodological choices underpinning the development of IBTool within the GLOSSA project:

1. Which forms of facilitation can Decision Support Systems (DSS) provide to Public Administrations (PAs) for monitoring sustainable development and guiding territorial transformation strategies?
2. How do DSS account for the uncertainty arising from value conflicts, differences in opinion, information gaps, and the operational limitations of sustainability indicators?

In response to these research questions, the GLOSSA knowledge system has been conceived as a decision support tool aimed at PAs, researchers, and professionals who use indicators for measuring sustainability in their projects. A short survey on sustainability assessment tools has been presented in Section 3 to answer the first research question, while Sections 4-5 were addressed to the second question by introducing the methodological workflow and operational steps of the IBTool software.

3. Research projects, platforms, and tools for urban sustainability assessment

As part of the software development process, an investigation was conducted into existing platforms, research projects, and indicator-based tools using a *snowballing technique*. The objective was to deepen current knowledge of similar solutions to enhance the performance of IBTool, highlighting its innovative contribution in overcoming limitations or strengthening capabilities associated with previous applications and methods. The investigation was structured by considering scientific contributions drawn from recent literature, research projects, online tools that use indicators to address various challenges, structured databases, and recent technological advancements (e.g., digital twins).

Table 1 presents seven selected cases that provided a foundation for developing preliminary ideas and addressing issues related to software development

Table 1. A survey of research projects consistent with IBTool

Project	Goal	Main features	Highlights	Link	Year
1. ECIU SMART-ER	Research and innovation ecosystem focused on urban/territorial challenges and SDGs	Challenge-based approach (1); use of indicators for smart cities and regions (2); integration of digital twins, big data (3); collaborative projects and living labs (4).	Participatory methodologies for defining and validating indicators (1); integration of real-time data and predictive analysis (2); scenario planning and multi-stakeholder evaluation (3).	https://www.eciu.eu/smart-er-for-researchers	2021
2. UrbanLab Torino – Geografie Metropolitane	Cartographic and information platform of Turin	Thematic maps and dashboards (1); comparison of neighbourhoods and urban areas (2); updating of institutional data sources and field research (3).	Georeferenced representation of KPIs (1); dashboards and interactive maps to communicate indicators value (2).	https://urbanlabtorino.it/mappe/geografie-metropolitane/	2020
3. Geodesignhub	Collaborative platform for geodesign and multi-scenario planning	Spatial analysis tools integrated with participatory approaches (1); collective design sessions and scenario co-creation (2); GIS data and thematic indicators (3).	Collaborative approach for scenarios definition (1); iterative methods for selecting and evaluating indicators (2).	https://www.geodesignhub.com/	2017
4. GRINS – Piattaforma Amelia	Digital platform for urban and spatial data management and analysis	Integrated environment for scenario simulation (1); institutional and open data sources collection (2); development and monitoring of urban research projects (3).	Methodologies for KPIs validation (1); use of standard data collection protocols (2).	https://grins.it/progetto/piattaforma-amelia	2022
5. Argaleo	Data analytics platform for areas such as mobility, energy, urban security, strategic planning	Big data analysis and interactive visualisations (1); custom dashboards for PAs and companies (2); real-time data collection from sensors and open data (3).	Advanced interface with maps, graphs and indicator filters (1); MCDA modules; real-time and scenario-based approach for improving decision-making at urban scale (2).	https://www.argaleo.com/en/	2020
6. NLAIC	Dedicated artificial intelligence network with projects in various sectors (health, energy, mobility)	ML algorithms and Advanced analytics (1); integration of indicators set for predictive assessment (2); dedicated tools for decision support (3).	AI/ML modules, uncertainty management and predictive analysis (1); KPI calculation for medium/long term assessment (2).	https://nlaic.com/en/	2024
7. CORDIS –	EU-funded	Use of indicators to monitor	Standardisation and	https://cordis	2016

Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures	project with focus on urban safety/innovation	projects output (1); risk management and infrastructure safety (2).	validation protocols for indicators (1); integration of risk assessment and stakeholder engagement (2).	europea.eu/press/2022/06/01/0700621
---	---	---	---	---

In a scientific landscape characterized by the growing demand for reliable, data-driven decision-making tools, a variety of research projects, platforms, and digital solutions have emerged that use indicators to address complex urban and territorial challenges. The investigation carried out enabled the exploration of a range of resources which, despite operating in different contexts, share the common goal of supporting DMs in monitoring, analyzing, and planning interventions aimed at improving sustainability and quality of life in cities.

From the ECIU SMART-ER programme, which focuses on local and regional challenges, two key aspects have emerged that have guided the development of IBTool: the challenge-driven approach, in which research projects are co-created with stakeholders, and the use of advanced technological solutions, such as digital twins, capable of simulating future scenarios and integrating real-time data. These elements highlight the need to develop agile platforms capable of incorporating large volumes of heterogeneous information and presenting it clearly to different types of users (technicians, administrators, and citizens).

The thematic mapping proposed by UrbanLab and Politecnico di Torino, on the other hand, underscores the importance of cartographic representation and spatial analysis, in which territorial information is aggregated and presented through intuitive interfaces based on open-source methods that ensure replicability (Lami et al., 2024). A focus on collaborative and interactive dynamics is also evident in *Geodesignhub*, which integrates design tools with participatory methodologies, once again emphasizing how crucial stakeholder involvement is in ensuring shared processes for selecting and validating indicators that are relevant to the local context. Although IBTool was not conceived within a spatial framework, the key features derived from these two projects relate to the collaborative logic useful for obtaining real-time impact assessments of meta-planning projects, as well as the idea of visualizing dashboards and structured repositories of open-source territorial indicators—not only to understand the main phenomena affecting monitored areas but also to enhance territorial cohesion (Stehle & Kitchin, 2019).

The platforms *Amelia* and *Argaleo*, by contrast, are more oriented towards real-time data analysis and management, employing digital twins and advanced dashboards to monitor key parameters related to mobility, security, energy, and other urban services (Charitonidou, 2022). The integration of sensor data with institutional databases highlights one of the most pressing needs identified in this study: the ability to collect, unify, and validate heterogeneous information to achieve a coherent understanding of the urban or territorial system.

Regarding the emerging technologies, the *Netherlands AI Coalition* (NLAIC) illustrates how Machine Learning (ML) can enhance predictive analysis and the capacity to identify patterns that are not immediately evident, providing critical insights for designing targeted actions in complex sectors such as healthcare, mobility, and energy transition. This underscores the importance of implementing data analysis techniques based on shared, validated, and operational knowledge bases for project evaluation and monitoring at different scales.

Finally, EU-funded research projects such as *Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures* (CORDIS no. 700621) confirm the trend of defining standards and guidelines for the use of indicators in security

and urban innovation contexts. The European perspective also underlines the importance of transparent reporting of results and the adoption of rigorous impact assessment methodologies to ensure that public funding generates tangible and replicable effects across different contexts.

The investigation conducted has provided valuable insights for the implementation of IBTool. Firstly, the ability to organize multiple sources of indicators and offer an interactive visualization of these through user-friendly and easily interpretable dashboards is a crucial element for system usability. Secondly, the experimentation with participatory and collaborative approaches, such as living labs and geodesign, highlights the necessity of incorporating modules for active stakeholder engagement, ensuring that the definition and validation of indicators genuinely respond to the real needs of urban contexts. Moreover, the increasing focus on collaborative governance processes, which generate high levels of uncertainty, suggests the implementation of tools capable of capturing potential divergences in opinion and integrating them into decision-making processes in a democratic manner (Meijer & Bolívar, 2015).

In summary, this investigation confirms the strategic role of indicator-based solutions in promoting sustainable development and improving decision-making processes in urban and territorial contexts. Drawing from the various projects and platforms examined, IBTool gains insights to enhance its flexibility, robustness, and ability to adapt to different contexts and users.

4. Methodology

The IBTool software is configured as a multi-criteria assessment system designed to support decision-making processes in monitoring territorial progress towards sustainability targets and evaluating sustainable urban transformation projects or scenarios. Conceived to integrate a structured set of indicators, IBTool enables the assessment and prioritization of interventions in alignment with the SDG11 targets. The tool employs scoring and ranking methodologies to determine the relevance and priority of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring a structured, data-driven approach to facilitate sustainable urban planning decisions.

The methodological process underpinning IBTool follows a collaborative and multi-stakeholder logic based on the quadruple helix model (Cavallini et al., 2016; Roman & Fellnhöfer, 2022) and was developed using the *AGILE* methodology (Misra et al., 2012). This approach involved an in-depth review of existing assessment tools, expert consultations, and focus groups, as well as empirical testing to validate its effectiveness. Specifically, in the *ex-ante* phase, the software aims to support the identification of critical intervention areas and the structuring of urban transformation projects, facilitating funding allocation and assessing proposals against Goal 11 criteria. In the *ex-post* phase, it enables the monitoring and certification of funded projects, ensuring the achievement of sustainability objectives and providing a coherent framework for performance and impact evaluation.

The development and testing activities related to IBTool have been organized within Work Package 3 (WP3) of GLOSSA, coordinated by UNINA with contributions from all research units. WP3 focuses on defining IBTool's multi-criteria methodology, prioritizing the indicators selected in WP2, and verifying its applicability across different urban contexts. The process also involves experts in assessment tools and multi-criteria analysis, ensuring a robust scientific framework. IBTool represents a key technical outcome of the GLOSSA project, offering an open-source decision-support system for sustainable urban planning and urban transformation.

In summary, the four main methods validated and tested by the research units and implemented in the software within WP3 are:

3. The classification of indicators based on qualitative evaluations using stated preference methods, including the *Delphi Fuzzy Method* (DFM), *Triangular Fuzzy Numbers* (TFN), and clustering algorithms (K-means);
4. The prioritization of indicators (weights) using the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) method known as the *Best Worst Method* (BWM);
5. Sustainability performance indices using the *Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution* (TOPSIS) method;
6. The impact assessment of scenarios or actual projects on the territories.

The following section (Section 4.1) provides a detailed description of IBTool's technical requirements.

4.1 IBTool technical requirements

IBTool is an open-source software developed within the GLOSSA project for the validation, selection, weighting, and evaluation of sustainability KPIs related to Goal 11 (SDG11). The software consists essentially of a client and a server and has been designed through user-friendly approach.

The client has been developed using *GDscript*, leveraging the flexibility offered by the *Godot* engine, which is released under the MIT license. This has enabled the creation of an intuitive interface optimized to reduce users' cognitive load, integrating indicators derived from sustainability protocols and scientific literature. To ensure greater autonomy and avoid external dependencies, data analysis algorithms such as K-means with *Naive Sharding* (Mayo, 2016) and decision-making methods such as BWM with the *simplex* linear programming algorithm (Rezaei, 2015), as well as the multi-criteria TOPSIS method (Hwang & Yoon, 1981; Behzadian et al., 2012), have been directly implemented within the client. This approach has resulted in a fully *stand-alone* software application, eliminating the need to install additional packages that might cause compatibility issues across different operating systems. In its current version, IBTool is fully compatible with both Windows and macOS systems.

The server, on the other hand, has been developed using *Python* and employs *Flask* for API management, communicating with an *SQLite* database for information storage. Client-server communication takes place via *WebSocket*, enabling real-time transmission of notifications and events without requiring the server to perform direct data processing. This architecture allows for a more streamlined and efficient management of operations. For deployment, *Ubuntu Linux-based* servers have been selected, providing a free and well-established open-source solution. Regarding distribution, IBTool will be available for download through a dedicated web page. The source code will be managed via *Git* and hosted on *GitHub* to promote transparency and collaboration within the open-source community. The technical documentation accompanying the official release will provide details on system requirements and the communication framework between the client and server.

Finally, to facilitate software migration between servers, dedicated tools have been developed in *BASH*, ensuring compatibility with *UNIX* systems. This choice enables easier deployment management and high platform portability. IBTool thus represents an innovative and accessible solution for sustainability indicator-based assessments, guaranteeing high performance and ease of use.

5. IBTool operational steps

The proposed Decision Support System (DSS) has been developed to assist PAs in selecting and prioritizing KPIs to evaluate the sustainability performance of neighbourhoods and buildings, as well as the impact of

urban projects on the territory. For this reason, IBTool is designed as a modular software capable of integrating both qualitative and quantitative methods, supporting iterative processes, and ensuring the involvement of various types of users (ranging from assessment experts to stakeholders) with differentiated levels of automation and transparency.

The IBTool workflow is structured into four main phases, subdivided into ten operational steps. The main phases are:

1. Data storage
2. Validation
3. Weighting
4. Impact/performance assessment

Each phase provides intermediate results that serve as the foundation for subsequent steps, ultimately delivering recommendations and decisions based on structured analyses, scenario comparisons, and multi-criteria approaches (Figure 1).

Figure 1. IBTool software methodological workflow

In the workflow, various multi-criteria methods, ML algorithms, and evaluation techniques have been implemented with the aim of: (i) supporting PAs; (ii) guiding expert groups and local communities; (iii)

facilitating decision-making across different stages of the decision-making process, either in a supportive, guiding, or decisive role, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. IBTool operational steps

Step	Software input	Methods/Tools	Users	Software output	DSS
1.Data Storage	Manual	Literature review	Super-User	Storage	Support
2.Validation - I round	Manual	Survey - Frequency analysis	Multi-User	Scoring	Support/Leading
3.Validation - II round	Automatic	Delphi Fuzzy	Black-boxed	Ranking	Leading
4.Validation - III round	Automatic	K-means + Naive Sharding algorithm	Black-boxed	Clustering	Leading/Decisive
5.Validation - IV round	Manual	Focus Group	Single-User	KPI selection	Leading
6.Weighting	Manual/Automatic	BWM (MCDA) with Focus Group	Single-User	Weights elicitation	Support/Leading
7.Performance Assessment - I round	Manual	Indicators measurement	Single-User	Storage	Support/Leading
8.Performance Assessment - II round	Automatic	TOPSIS (MCDA)	Black-boxed	Ranking	Support/Leading
9.Impact Assessment - I round	Manual	Indicators measurement	Single-User	Storage	Support
2.Validation - I round	Manual	Survey - Frequency analysis	Multi-User	Scoring	Support/Leading
10.Impact Assessment - II round	Automatic	Scenario Analysis	Black-boxed	Percentage variation	Leading

The following Subsections (5.1 – 5.4) provide a detailed description of the ten operational steps within their respective four main phases.

5.1 Data Storage (Step 1)

In the first operational step, reserved for system’s Administrators henceforth referred to as Super-Users, the collection and classification of SDG11 indicators — selected within GLOSSA’s WP2 — are carried out. This phase is based on a comprehensive review of the relevant literature to ensure that the collected indicators have a solid scientific foundation and align with the project objectives.

In the experimental prototype adopted by GLOSSA, the focus has been placed on urban sustainability indicators within SDG11. However, IBTool’s architecture will be sufficiently flexible to accommodate different

sets of indicators. In the presented *version 0.7.1*, once the initial indicator definition phase is complete, Super-Users can enter data directly into the client via an interface that allows them to compile the main characteristics of each indicator or upload specifically structured lists in *json* format from the server.

As shown in Figure 2, each indicator is characterised by the following items:

- *ID*. A unique identifier that allows the indicator to be traced and managed within the database.
- *Target*. Specifies the numerical identifier of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) target.
- *Categoria (Category)*. Identifies the macro-area or thematic domain to which the indicator belongs.
- *Tema*. Defines the specific evaluation scope of the indicator within its macro-category.
- *Descrizione (Description)*. Provides an explanatory text detailing the meaning and purpose of the indicator, essential for describing the observed phenomenon to non-expert users.
- *Unità di misura (Unit of measure)*. Specifies the metric used to quantify the indicator, as derived from literature analysis or NSATs. This can include quantitative or qualitative scales, semantic labels (e.g. Likert scale), or other types.
- *Calcolo (Formulas)*. Describes how the indicator's value is determined based on literature analysis or sustainability protocols (e.g. "EU-SILC survey").
- *Scala di analisi (Analysis scale)*. Specifies the territorial level or the minimum spatial unit at which the indicator is calculated (building or neighbourhood).
- *Fase di utilizzo (Phase of use)*. Indicates the stage of the decision-making process where the indicator may be useful (monitoring or evaluation).
- *Fonte (Source)*. Lists bibliographic references or institutions that produce or curate the data relevant to defining the indicator.
- *Link*. Provides precise references (URLs) for accessing more specific information (metadata, official reports, databases, sustainability protocols).
- *Preset*. A field that Super-Users can use to select indicators to be submitted to users for the validation phase.
- *Note Glossa (Glossa comments)*. A section for additional annotations, internal references, or comments useful for Super-Users in co-editing the database.
- *UUID*. An alphanumeric string ensuring the unique identification of the indicator within the server.
- *Modificati (Modified)*. Records when the indicator was last updated or modified, tracking the revision history.

Thanks to this structure, IBTool facilitates the creation of a well-organised repository of indicators, ensuring that each item is defined in a transparent and traceable manner. Furthermore, IBTool allows only Super-Users to view the list of collected indicators through a summary panel that provides access to the cloud.

The Super-User primarily works locally, with the option to access the list of indicators stored on the server or update it by submitting modifications, making them available to all other users. In real time, the system tracks interventions, notifying users of any updated, deleted, or newly added indicators while recording the date and time of each modification (Figure 3).

This selective sharing approach allows Super-Users to maintain control over the preliminary phases of indicator entry and potential revision before making them available to the entire working team. This facilitates and supports collaborative work, reduces conflicts, and ensures that the database evolves consistently with various operational requirements.

Finally, from the indicator panel, IBTool allows Super-Users to assign a *preset* to the indicators they wish to select based on specific validation sessions. IBTool thus makes the entire list of indicators available, which can be used either in its entirety or partially as input for the subsequent phases of the workflow.

11.1.1.1
 ▼ Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni con problemi strutturali o problemi di umidità

Target Categoria ID

L'indicatore misura la percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni che presentano almeno uno tra i seguenti problemi: a) problemi strutturali dell'abitazione (es. tetti, soffitti, pavimenti) b) problemi di umidità (es. muri, pavimenti, fondamenta).

Tema

Unità di misura

Calcolo

Scala di analisi

Fase di utilizzo

Fonte

Link a fonti

<input type="text" value="ISTAT 2023 (metadati)"/>	<input type="text" value="https://www.istat.it/it/benessere-e-sostenibilit%C3%A0/obiettivi-di-sviluppo-sost"/>	<input type="button" value="Apri il link"/>	<input type="button" value="🗑"/>
<input type="text" value="ISTAT 2023 (Rapporto ISTAT)"/>	<input type="text" value="https://www.istat.it/storage/rapporti-tematici/sdgs/2023/Rapporto-SDGs-"/>	<input type="button" value="Apri il link"/>	<input type="button" value="🗑"/>

Preset

Note Glossa

UUID

Modificato

Figure 2. IBTool indicators panel (software screenshot)

File Zoom Informazioni Pannelli GLOSSA mode

Gestione database indicatori

Salva Auto allinea Mostra Elimina Mostra Sovrascrivi

Locali
Totale: 62

- ▶ 11.1.1.1 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni con problemi strutturali o problemi di umidità
- ▶ 11.1.1.1.1 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni sovraffollate
- ▶ 11.1.1.3 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni con rumore dai vicini o dalla strada
- ▶ 11.1.1.4 Qualità acustica dell'edificio
- ▶ 11.1.1.5 Indice di disponibilità di spazi esterni nell'abitazione
- ▶ 11.1.1.6 Metri quadrati di spazio esterno comune per occupante nelle abitazioni occupate
- ▶ 11.1.1.2 Aree comuni: spazi di relazione e spazi comuni
- ▶ 11.1.1.8 Accesso agli spazi pubblici
- ▶ 11.1.1.9 Adattabilità funzionale
- ▶ 11.1.2.3 Sovraccarico dei costi abitativi

Sul cloud
Totale: 62

- ▶ 11.1.1.1 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni con problemi strutturali o problemi di umidità
- ▶ 11.1.1.1.1 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni sovraffollate
- ▶ 11.1.1.3 Percentuale di persone che vivono in abitazioni con rumore dai vicini o dalla strada
- ▶ 11.1.1.4 Qualità acustica dell'edificio
- ▶ 11.1.1.5 Indice di disponibilità di spazi esterni nell'abitazione
- ▶ 11.1.1.6 Metri quadrati di spazio esterno comune per occupante nelle abitazioni occupate
- ▶ 11.1.1.2 Aree comuni: spazi di relazione e spazi comuni
- ▶ 11.1.1.8 Accesso agli spazi pubblici
- ▶ 11.1.1.9 Adattabilità funzionale
- ▶ 11.1.2.3 Sovraccarico dei costi abitativi

Lista indicatori
 Lista indicatori da server aggiornata.

Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca | PRIN 2022 - GLOSSA | CLP ES3D/231027006 | Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II | La raccolta delle

Figure 3. IBTool indicators database management panel (software screenshot)

It is important to highlight that, at this stage, IBTool collaboratively supports the management of the indicator database by Super-Users working on its identification and classification.

5.2 Validation (Step 2 - 5)

In the validation round I, after selecting indicators for evaluation by experts and stakeholders, IBTool enables the visualization of the survey session, which the Super-User can generate in the previous step through the dedicated panel within the interface referred to as *Gestione Sessioni e Analisi dei dati*. Authentication is performed via an activation code provided by the Super-User to respondents, who, upon entering it, gain access to the main client interface to complete the questionnaire.

In the main interface, Single-Users see a list of indicators on the left, organized by themes and categories corresponding to the relevant targets (Figure 4). Each indicator is accompanied by an information sheet detailing its specific attributes. Users are then asked to express a preference based on the two criteria defined by GLOSSA for indicator validation:

- Relevance of the indicator concerning the evaluation goal,
- Calculability of the indicator in the given territorial context.

The semantic evaluation scale allows respondents to assign three qualitative judgments of relevance and calculability: "low," "medium," and "high", with an additional option "I don't know" for cases of uncertainty or lack of sufficient information regarding specific indicators.

Moreover, Single-Users can report any issues related to the indicators by selecting from predefined options:

- No issues,
- Data unavailable,
- Data unreliable,
- Partial data,
- Proprietary data,
- Other issues (with an optional text comment for further clarification).

Within this multi-stakeholder process, IBTool facilitates the completion of the questionnaire through a dynamic tutorial designed to explain the various components and how to use the panels within the interface. Once the questionnaire is completed, the Single-User has the option to review their responses to the different indicators and submit the evaluation results to the GLOSSA server via the "Submit Responses" button, which becomes accessible only upon completion of the questionnaire.

The client performs a Frequency Analysis (FA) of the responses in real time, thereby generating an initial level of insight that translates into a scoring system for the semantic judgments of Relevance, Calculability, and Issues.

In the validation round II, using the information obtained from the questionnaires and the results from the AF as input, IBTool transforms qualitative data into quantitative data through the FDM, which has been adopted to rigorously manage the validation phase, reducing uncertainty associated with expert judgments and promoting the achievement of shared consensus (Padilla-Rivera et al., 2021). The integration of the Delphi method (traditionally based on expert consultation iterations) with fuzzy logic allows capturing nuances and ambiguities often present in qualitative decision-making processes (Murray et al., 1985; Kuo & Chen, 2008).

Figure 4. IBTool panel for validation survey (software screenshot)

The following describes the operational steps of the DFM as implemented by IBTool.

The first step of the process involves the numerical translation of the input data. For each indicator and validation criterion, IBTool collects frequency data of the responses provided by the participants, assigning a numerical value to each semantic judgment based on the Saaty scale. The ratings were established as follows:

- "None" = 1,
- "Medium" = 5,
- "High" = 9.

If a participant selects the response "I don't know," IBTool applies a score of -1 to the total number of respondents, thus reducing the sample size considered and avoiding penalizing the indicator's value. This rule ensures that ratings are calculated only based on the actual expertise of the respondents.

Subsequently, the calculation of the TFN for each indicator and criterion takes place. This number is defined through three key values: the lower bound "a," corresponding to the lowest score selected; the upper bound "c," representing the highest score; and the central value "b," calculated as the weighted average of the selected categories, relating the frequency of responses to the actual number of participants.

Once the TFNs are determined for each criterion, the next step is their merging, for each indicator, via a fuzzy extender (Fuzzy Synthetic Extent). To obtain a unique value, the two triangular fuzzy numbers are combined through an average, allowing the result to be a representative value that considers both criteria with equal weight.

After this phase, the defuzzification process is applied, which transforms the TFN triple into a *crisp* value "D," representing the composite index of relevance and computability. This is calculated using the center of gravity method, with "D" being the arithmetic mean of the three fuzzy number values. The result of this procedure generates an first quantitative-qualitative indicators ordering based on the obtained *crisp* score and their maximization according to the validation criteria.

During the validation round III, IBTool implements the K-means clustering algorithm in real-time to organize the indicators into homogeneous groups. The clustering is performed based on the *crisp* values obtained from the DFM and involves the arrangement of indicators into three main clusters: (i) “indicators to be selected,” characterized by high Crisp scores; (ii) “selectable indicators” with intermediate scores; (iii) “indicators to be discarded,” which have lower scores.

The K-means ML algorithm, refined through the *Naive Sharding* initialization procedure operates by selecting “K” potential initial centroids, determined based on the number of predefined clusters (Mayo, 2016). The procedure enables the initial starting points to be in positions that respect the actual data trends in their ordering. Once the initial centroids are defined, each point in the dataset is assigned to the nearest center by calculating the Euclidean distance and assessing proximity to the initial centroids. After the assignment procedure is completed, each of the “K” centroids is repositioned through the average of the points it belongs to. After the repositioning of centroids, the algorithm revisits the entire dataset to reassign points to cluster centers, as some points may be closer to a different center. The reassignment and repositioning process continues iterating until the centroids stabilize, meaning the data assignments no longer show significant shifts. At that point, the algorithm is considered convergent, and the K identified groups are final.

In the validation round IV, the focus is on a direct, qualitative comparison phase, where a group of experts or the single DM deeply analyses the results derived from the previous phases. Therefore, the results obtained through quantitative and automated methods are reread and discussed with the participants, who have the opportunity to provide reasoned feedback and engage in discussions about the selection or exclusion of validated indicators.

The software interface in the section *Gestione Sessioni e Analisi dei dati* (figure 5) presents five data configurations that facilitate discussion. It allows indicators to be displayed in rankings following different logics, with the first three based on the frequency of responses to the questionnaires, where the indicators are evaluated with respect to computability, relevance, and problematic issues, and the last ranks the indicators in the three clusters resulting from the K-means, according to their degree of selection expressed through the composite relevance and computability index.

At the conclusion of the discussion, a final selection is made in which the group or the DM decides which indicators will be included in the evaluation system as KPIs. By default, IBTool proposes an initial selection that includes all the indicators from the first cluster, i.e., those rated as most relevant and computable. However, this selection is not binding as it is possible to modify, add, or remove indicators based on qualitative feedback and the specificities of the context. A limitation of IBTool requires the user to select a maximum of 10 KPIs to avoid inconsistencies in the subsequent weighting phase. The formalization of this selection must be documented in a report that clarifies the reasoning behind the decisions made, ensuring transparency and traceability of the entire validation process, which combines quantitative methods and moments of qualitative discussion.

Figure 5. IBTool panel for sessions management and data analytics (software screenshot)

Finally, the validation round IV serves as a bridge between the large amount of aggregated data from the previous phases and the actual planning or policy-making needs, ensuring that the chosen indicators are not only statistically robust but also effectively address the needs and objectives of the context in which they will be applied.

5.3 Weighting (Step 6)

The BWM is an MCDA approach developed by Rezaei (2015) and used to determine the importance of different criteria in a decision-making problem, following four structured steps (Rezaei, 2015). The process begins with identifying the relevant criteria for the decision. Next, the DM selects the most important criterion (best) and the least important one (worst). At this point, a comparison is made to determine how much more important the best criterion is compared to all others (best to others), and then how much more important each criterion is compared to the worst (others to worst). These comparisons are used to create a set of mathematical equations, which are then solved to determine the optimal weights for each criterion, while ensuring consistency in the decision-making process. One of the main advantages of BWM is that it requires fewer comparisons than traditional methods, such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), making it faster and simpler to use, even for non-experts.

The BWM has been integrated into IBTool through the interface panel called *Sessione Valutazione* as shown in Figure 6. This panel is divided into three parts: on the left, a description of the main objective and instructions about the method are provided to inform the user; the central window allows the Single-User to fill in the necessary fields to carry out the evaluation process with the BWM; while the third part of the panel, on the right, displays the results in terms of the consistency index and the weights obtained upon completing the phase of assigning semantic judgments from 1 to 9 according to the Saaty scale.

Figure 6. IBTool panel for BWM (software screenshot)

The BWM corresponds to phase 6 of the process implemented in the software and requires manual data input from the Single-Users, who must complete the BWM survey by providing their judgments in a focus group facilitated by experts. The maximum number of indicators that can be evaluated using the BWM has been set to 10, as cognitive effort increases with the number of items to evaluate, leading to more frequent inconsistencies and making the decision-making phase more complex (Saaty, 2001). The client then calculates the equations underlying the method and automatically returns the elicited weights of the indicators to the users.

In this phase, the role of the DSS is to support the DMs in defining the priorities of the KPIs, but also to guide the balancing of composite indices that are effectively tied to territorial contexts or priority evaluation objectives, which will be produced in the final stages of the decision-making process facilitated by IBTool.

5.4 Performance/Impact assessment (Step 7 - 10)

Steps 7 and 8 allow users to evaluate the performance of decision alternatives (e.g., neighborhoods, projects, areas of interest, etc.) through a composite index characterized by the combination of the indicators selected, validated, and weighted in the previous phases. In particular, in step 7, the user is required to input the values of the KPIs, which have been preliminarily calculated, into a dedicated form within the panel called *Immissione valori alternative* (Figure 7).

Figure 7. IBTool panel for indicators value input (software screenshot)

The aggregation of the weights with the indicator values occurs at the end of the input process using the TOPSIS method, which allows for the calculation of the performance index by comparing the alternatives of the decision problem. The performance histograms, derived from comparing the alternatives with respect to each indicator (on the left), and the composite indices of the alternatives (on the right), are displayed in the area beneath the interface.

In the second panel of step 7, called *Controllo valutazione*, it is also possible to set benchmark thresholds independent of the ideal negative and positive values determined by the TOPSIS method for each indicator (Figure 8). The flexibility in choosing thresholds that do not come from direct comparisons between the alternatives of the decision problem allows for balancing the indicator values by considering different geographic and socio-demographic contexts. This approach promotes fairness by accounting for territorial differences and underpins the scalability of the knowledge system designed by GLOSSA.

To conclude, the third panel — called *Panoramica delle performance alternative*—highlights the value of the composite performance indices for each alternative, allowing the user to redefine the direction of the indicators and view, in real time, the changes in the rankings of the alternatives and indicators through a bar chart (Figure 9).

A new Decision Support Tool for assessing cities sustainability levels: the IBTool software

Figure 8. IBTool panel for evaluation control (software screenshot)

Figure 9. IBTool panel for sustainability performance checking through bar charts (software screenshot)

The role of the DSS in these two steps is twofold: on one hand, it guides the DMs in identifying areas of criticality and improvement in territories through the interpretation of composite indices value; on the other hand, it supports the generation of different sustainability scenarios based on variations in the benchmark thresholds set by the comparison of alternatives.

Steps 9 and 10, which are still under development, will allow for the evaluation of the impacts of urban-scale plans, programs, or projects with respect to the selected SDG11 indicators, using the weights obtained in step 6 through the BWM. These weights are intended as coefficients of relative importance and will serve to determine an ordering of the indicators. In this way, it will be possible to assess a percentage variation in the normalized indicator values determined by the impact of the planned project actions, in a scenario planning logic, or actual impacts for the evaluation of direct effects.

The final phases of IBTool play a supportive role, inherent in the possibility to storage indicators values in different time-scenarios and to guide the redefinition of sustainability directions or confirm the effectiveness of the actions being evaluated in terms of alignment with the targets of Goal 11.

6. Conclusions and further development

IBTool is an experimental software developed within the GLOSSA project, designed to manage decision-making processes at the urban scale through the storage, selection, prioritization, and evaluation of SDG11 indicators. During its development phases, the software has been modified and implemented multiple times, incorporating contributions from the research team, academic experts, and public administration testers following the collaborative *AGILE* methodology, and is presented here in its *version 0.7.1*.

The experience gained so far with the development of the prototype and the initial results from the GLOSSA project have demonstrated how an integrated evaluation approach, which includes both qualitative-quantitative methods for indicator validation, MCDA, and open-source decision support tools, can guide urban sustainability decision-making processes in a more transparent and collaborative manner.

The transition from divergence to convergence is another potential feature of IBTool's facilitative role. As perspectives are refined, options are reassessed and, in many cases, reimaged. The act of capturing and visually representing contributions acts as a catalyst for creativity, enabling the emergence of novel solutions (Jelassi and Beauclair 1987). In this way, IBTool is instrumental in fostering an environment where new ideas can evolve within the group's collective understanding.

In this perspective, IBTool promotes a key aspect of "soft" negotiation by encouraging participants to shift from a strictly personal perspective to one that incorporates elements of others' viewpoints. This dynamic interplay enhances the group's ability to achieve a more holistic and shared understanding of the issue at hand. The public display mechanism further supports this by dissociating contributions from their originators, ensuring that viewpoints are assessed on their intrinsic merit rather than on the status or influence of the contributor. Nevertheless, where appropriate, contributors can claim ownership of their ideas and actively advocate for their adoption.

While each of these elements—linked to anonymity and the transitional nature of the model—offers distinct benefits, they are also mutually reinforcing. For instance, the ability to work with transitional objects such as IBTool enhances procedural justice, and the structured yet flexible environment provided by the tool actively supports the generation of innovative options. In this way, IBTool does not merely assist in structuring

group interactions but plays a transformative role in guiding groups towards more inclusive, creative, and equitable decision-making processes.

The main limitations of the proposed approach are both methodological and technical and will be partly overcome in future developments of the project, considering the time and resources available.

From a methodological perspective, indeed, the primary challenge lies in refining the validation procedures to make IBTool increasingly suitable for managing situations characterized by fragmented or hard-to-obtain information, typical of urban contexts (Poli et al., 2024). The operational limit of 10 KPIs manageable by the software in step 3 (weighting), currently addressed through organizing the decision-making process into different rounds of thematic evaluation, could be overcome by introducing new weighting, optimization, and informed guidance functionalities in the indicator selection processes.

Additionally, the generalization of the database architecture will form the foundation for extending the software's use beyond current experiments, making it more flexible and modular by allowing for the reorganization of categorized indicators in relation to other SDGs or operational indicators framework.

At the same time, the introduction of multi-user sessions will enable more dynamic management of prioritization processes, enhancing the ability to handle information collected from heterogeneous users (political decision-makers, stakeholders, technicians, researchers, investors, etc.) and aggregating results with hybrid multicriteria methods (Martínez López et al., 2023). In this perspective, a multi-stakeholder mode will also be implemented for the construction of input indicators, increasing their coherence with contextually defined urban sustainability objectives, allowing for more complex evaluation iterations where the definition of KPIs is crucial to participatory and shared decision-making.

Future technological developments will focus on introducing a complete *suite* of improvements designed to enhance functionality, accessibility, and security. Initially, a robust multilingual localization system will enable users to use the DSS in various geographic locations and for different types of decision problems, ensuring a more inclusive experience.

Additionally, an advanced authorization system will include intermediate roles between Super-User and Single-User, offering greater flexibility in managing access and responsibilities. Access to the validation survey results, for example, will allow users to easily find relevant information, promoting transparency and raising awareness of emerging issues. Simultaneously, automatic backups and advanced server management tools will be implemented to ensure data integrity and the overall performance of the system.

To improve result management, the automatic report generation feature will further simplify the validation and evaluation process by producing detailed documentation about the session activities. Finally, the user interface will be optimized through the implementation of *UX* design, further simplifying navigation and making the software experience more intuitive and enjoyable.

In the future, the extension to application case studies, foreseen by the GLOSSA project yet to be tested, will offer additional opportunities to test and improve IBTool, bringing to light areas for advancement in both methodological robustness, with the implementation of other types of MCDA methods, and algorithmic enhancement by refining clustering procedures.

The ambition is to consolidate IBTool as a decision support tool capable of combining scientific robustness, operational versatility, and the ability to foster more inclusive governance processes, oriented towards achieving further sustainability targets set by urban agendas.

Acknowledgement

This contribution has received funding by the Research Project of National Relevance (PRIN) GLOSSA - *GLOcal knowledge System for Sustainability Assessment of urban projects* (CUP E53D23010270006), coordinated by POLITO, Principal Investigator: Francesca Abastante; UNINA research unit leader: Giuliano Poli; UNICA research unit leader: Francesco Piras. The authors want to thank all the team members of GLOSSA project which helped to develop the software and provide insights to consolidate the methodological choices.

Author contributions

G.P.: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization, Data curation, Visualization; in particular, G.P. has primary focused and written in cooperation with co-authors the following article Sections: 1, 2, 4, 5, 5.3, 5.4, and 6. **S.C.:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Data curation, Methodology, Visualization; in particular, S.C. has primary focused and written in cooperation with co-authors the following article Sections: 3, 4, 5.1, 5.2, and 6. **D.D.:** Writing – review & editing, Formal Analysis, Software Development; in particular, D.D. has primary focused and written in cooperation with co-authors the following article Sections: 4.1, and 6.

Bibliography

- Abastante, F. (2023). Limits and perspectives of Neighbourhood Sustainable Assessment Tools (NSATS) in sustainable urban design. *Valori e Valutazioni*, 32, 31–43. <https://doi.org/10.48264/vvsiev-20233204>
- Ackermann F, Eden C (2021) Group Support Systems: Concepts to Practice. In: Kilgour, D.M., Eden, C. (eds) *Handbook of Group Decision and Negotiation*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49629-6_59
- Bachmann, N., Tripathi, S., Brunner, M., & Jodlbauer, H. (2022). The contribution of data-driven technologies in achieving the sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 14(5), 2497. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14052497>
- Behzadian, M., Khanmohammadi Otaghsara, S., Yazdani, M., & Ignatius, J. (2012). A state-of-the-art survey of TOPSIS applications. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 39(17), 13051–13069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2012.05.056>
- Bottero, M., Caprioli, C., Cotella, G., & Santangelo, M. (2019). Sustainable Cities: A Reflection on Potentialities and Limits based on Existing Eco-Districts in Europe. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5794. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205794>
- Bullock, J. B. (2019). Artificial intelligence, discretion, and bureaucracy. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 49(7), 751–761. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074019856123>
- Busch, P. A., & Henriksen, H. Z. (2018). Digital discretion: A systematic literature review of ICT and street-level discretion. *Information Polity*, 23(1), 3–28. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ip-170050>
- Camagni, R., Capello, R., & Nijkamp, P. (1998). Towards sustainable city policy: An economy-environment technology nexus. *Ecological Economics*, 24(1), 103–118. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0921-8009\(97\)00032-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0921-8009(97)00032-3)
- Carter, L., Yoon, V., & Liu, D. (2022). Analyzing e-government design science artifacts: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Information Management*, 62, 102430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102430>
- Cerreta, M., De Toro, P., & Fusco, G. L. (2014). Integrated assessment for sustainable choices. *SCIENZE REGIONALI*, 1, 111–141. <https://doi.org/10.3280/scr2014-s01006>

- Charitonidou, M. (2022). Urban scale digital twins in data-driven society: Challenging digital universalism in urban planning decision-making. *International Journal of Architectural Computing*, 20(2), 238–253. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14780771211070005>
- Cinelli, M., Kadziński, M., Gonzalez, M., & Słowiński, R. (2020). How to support the application of multiple criteria decision analysis? Let us start with a comprehensive taxonomy. *Omega*, 96, 102261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2020.102261>
- Dawodu, A., Cheshmehzangi, A., Sharifi, A., & Oladejo, J. (2022). Neighborhood sustainability assessment tools: Research trends and forecast for the built environment. *Sustainable Futures*, 4, 100064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sftr.2022.100064>
- Dizdaroglu D. (2017). The Role of Indicator-Based Sustainability Assessment in Policy and the Decision-Making Process: A Review and Outlook. *Sustainability*, 9, 1018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9061018>
- Dörfler V (2021) Looking Back on a Framework for Thinking About Group Support Systems. In: Kilgour, D.M., Eden, C. (eds) *Handbook of Group Decision and Negotiation*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49629-6_32
- Employment European Committee of the Regions: Commission for Social Policy, Cavallini, S., Soldi, R., Friedl, J., & Volpe, M. (2016). *Using the quadruple helix approach to accelerate the transfer of research and innovation results to regional growth*. European Committee of the Regions.
- Fusco Girard, L., Cerreta, M., & De Toro, P. (2014). Integrated assessment for sustainable choices. *Scienze regionali: Italian Journal of regional Science: 13, supplemento 1, 2014*, 111-141.
- Greco, S., Mousseau, V., Stefanowski, J., & Zopounidis, C. (2022). Roman słowiński and his research program: Intelligent decision support systems between operations research and artificial intelligence. In *Multiple Criteria Decision Making* (pp. 1–27). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-96318-7_1
- Henriksen, H. Z. (2017). One step forward and two steps back: E-government policies in practice. In *Public Administration and Information Technology* (pp. 79–97). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-61762-6_4
- Hwang, C.-L., & Yoon, K. (1981). Methods for multiple attribute decision making. In *Lecture Notes in Economics and Mathematical Systems* (pp. 58–191). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-48318-9_3
- Keenan, P. B., & Jankowski, P. (2019). Spatial Decision Support Systems: Three decades on. *Decision Support Systems*, 116, 64–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2018.10.010>
- Kitchin, R., Lauriault, T. P., & McArdle, G. (2015). Knowing and governing cities through urban indicators, city benchmarking and real-time dashboards. *Regional Studies, Regional Science*, 2(1), 6–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681376.2014.983149>
- Kuo, Y.-F., & Chen, P.-C. (2008). Constructing performance appraisal indicators for mobility of the service industries using Fuzzy Delphi Method. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 35(4), 1930–1939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2007.08.068>
- Lami, I. M., Abastante, F., Gaballo, M., Mecca, B., & Todella, E. (2023). Fostering sustainable cities through additional SDG11-related indicators. *Valori e Valutazioni*, 32, 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.48264/vvsiev-20233205>
- Lami, I.M., Abastante, F., Mecca, B., Todella, E. (2024). Maps and SDG11: A complex but possible relationship. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, Vol. 19, No. 4, pp. 1217-1237. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijstdp.190401>
- Marienfheldt, J. (2024). Does digital government hollow out the essence of street-level bureaucracy? A systematic literature review of how digital tools' foster curtailment, enablement and continuation of street-level decision-making. *Social Policy & Administration*, 58(5), 831–855. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spol.12991>
- Martínez López, L., Ishizaka, A., Qin, J., & Álvarez Carrillo, P. A. (2023). Multiple-Criteria Decision-Making sorting method. In *Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Sorting Methods* (pp. 13–49). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978->

- Mayo, M. M. (2016). *An Arithmetic-Based Deterministic Centroid Initialization Method for the kMeans Clustering Algorithm*. https://csuepress.columbusstate.edu/theses_dissertations/241
- Mecca, B., Gaballo, M., Todella, E. (2023) Measuring and evaluating urban sustainability. *Valori e Valutazioni* 32, pp. 17–29. https://siev.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/03_MECCA-ET-AL.pdf
- Meijer, A., & Bolívar, M. P. R. (2015). Governing the smart city: A review of the literature on smart urban governance. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 82(2), 392–408. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852314564308>
- Mirani, A. (2023). Evaluation of neighbourhood sustainability assessment tools for practicing on an existing neighbourhood in Great Paris. *Building Simulation Conference Proceedings*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2023.1572>
- Misra, S., Kumar, V., Kumar, U., Fantazy, K., & Akhter, M. (2012). Agile software development practices: Evolution, principles, and criticisms. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 29(9), 972–980. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02656711211272863>
- Murray, T. J., Pipino, L. L., & van Gigch, J. P. (1985). A pilot study of fuzzy set modification of Delphi*. *Human Systems Management*, 5(1), 76–80. <https://doi.org/10.3233/hsm-1985-5111>
- Orlikowski, W. J., & Iacono, C. S. (2001). Research commentary: Desperately seeking the “IT” in IT research—a call to theorizing the IT artifact. *Information Systems Research*, 12(2), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.12.2.121.9700>
- Padilla-Rivera, A., do Carmo, B. B. T., Arcese, G., & Merveille, N. (2021). Social circular economy indicators: Selection through fuzzy delphi method. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 26, 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2020.09.015>
- Panosso, A. da S., Miron, L. I. G., Delsante, I., & Tzortzopoulos, P. (2023, November 17). BALANCING PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES IN NEIGHBOURHOOD SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT. *SIMPÓSIO NACIONAL DE GESTÃO E ENGENHARIA URBANA*. <https://doi.org/10.46421/singeurb.v4i00.3608>
- Phillis, Y. A., Kouikoglou, V. S., & Verdugo, C. (2017). Urban sustainability assessment and ranking of cities. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 64, 254–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.03.002>
- Poli, G., Cuntò, S., & Muccio, E. (2024). A data-driven approach to monitor sustainable development transition in Italian regions through SDG 11 indicators. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (pp. 337–355). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65285-1_22
- Poveda C.A., Lipsett M.G., A Review of Sustainability Assessment and Sustainability/Environmental Rating Systems and Credit Weighting Tools, *Journal of Sustainable Development*, Vol. 4, No. 6, 2011, pp. 36–55. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jsd.v4n6p36>
- Pulgar Rubilar, P., Jordán Vidal, M. M., Blanco Fernández, D., Osorio Ramirez, M., Perillán Torres, L., Lizana Vial, M., Lobos Calquin, D., Pardo Fabregat, F., & Navarro Pedreño, J. (2023). Neighbourhood sustainability assessment tools for sustainable cities and communities, a literature review—new trends for new requirements. *Buildings*, 13(11), 2782. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13112782>
- Rezaei, J. (2015). Best-worst multi-criteria decision-making method. *Omega*, 53, 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2014.11.009>
- Roman, M., & Fellnhöfer, K. (2022). Facilitating the participation of civil society in regional planning: Implementing quadruple helix model in Finnish regions. *Land Use Policy*, 112, 105864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105864>
- Saaty, T. L. (2001). Fundamentals of the analytic hierarchy process. In *Managing Forest Ecosystems* (pp. 15–35). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-9799-9_2
- Simon, H. A. (2012). *The new science of management decision: The ford distinguished lectures, V3*
- Stehle, S., & Kitchin, R. (2019). Real-time and archival data visualisation techniques in city dashboards. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 34(2), 344–366.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2019.1594823>

Victor, P., Hanna, S., & Kubursi, A. (1998). How Strong is Weak Sustainability? In *Economy & Environment* (pp. 195–210). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-3188-1_12

Zamanidou, A., Magliozzi, A., & Fokaides, P. (2024). From buildings to neighborhoods: Upscaling smartness assessment for enhanced sustainability. *2024 9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.23919/splitech61897.2024.10612353>